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Leukotriene activation in the blood of humans with high CRP.

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The acute phase protein C-reactive protein (CRP) is an essential component of the early innate immune response that senses and announces physiologic danger. CRP level is strongly correlated with risk for heart attack (cardiovascular disease). We identified activation of gene products of the leukotriene pathway in humans with high blood CRP level. Activation of innate immune system is evident in humans with elevated CRP.